

**ILMIY VA
INNOVATSION
TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2026, № 3 (Май-Июнь)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
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**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

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MORPHOMETRIC COMPARISON OF HEPATIC ALTERATIONS DURING PREGNANCY IN EXPERIMENTAL ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY

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Abstract. Kidney diseases observed during pregnancy have a significant negative impact on the structure and function of the liver. This study evaluated morphometric and histopathological changes in the liver of pregnant albino rats with experimental acute renal failure. 60 7-month-old female rats were involved in the experiment. Histological analysis showed vacuolation of the hepatocyte cytoplasm, disruption of the structure of the central vein, dilation of the hepatic sinusoids, and increased Kupfer cell activity. The results obtained confirm that acute renal failure causes significant pathological changes in the liver parenchyma.

Keywords: Acute renal failure, pregnancy, liver morphometry, hepatocyte, Kupffer cells.

МОРФОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ СРАВНЕНИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ ПЕЧЕНИ ВО ВРЕМЯ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ ПРИ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ ОСТРОЙ ТРАВМЕ ПОЧЕК

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Аннотация. Заболевания почек, наблюдаемые во время беременности, оказывают значительное негативное влияние на структуру и функцию печени. В данном исследовании оценивались морфометрические и гистопатологические изменения в печени беременных крыс-альбиносов с экспериментальной острой почечной недостаточностью. К эксперименту были привлечены 60 7-месячных

самок крýс. Гистологический анализ показал вакуоляцию цитоплазмы гепатоцитов, нарушение структуры центральной вены, дилатацию синусоидов печени и повышение активности клеток Купфера. Полученные результаты подтверждают, что острая почечная недостаточность вызывает значительные патологические изменения в паренхиме печени.

Ключевые слова: Острая почечная недостаточность, беременность, морфометрия печени, гепатоцит, клетки Купфера.

**ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛ ЎТКИР БУЙРАК ЗАРАРЛАНИШИДА
ҲОМИЛАДОРЛИК ДАВРИДА ЖИГАР ЎЗГАРИШЛАРИНИ
МОРФОМЕТРИК ТАҚҚОСЛАШ
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Аннотация. Ҳомиладорлик даврида кузатиладиган буйрак касалликлари жигарнинг тузилиши ва фаолиятига сезиларли даражада салбий таъсир кўрсатади. Ушбу тадқиқотда экспериментал ўткир буйрак етишмовчилиги бўлган ҳомиладор оқ зотсиз каламушлар жигаридаги морфометрик ва гистопатологик ўзгаришлар баҳоланди. Тажрибага 60 та 7 ойлик урғочи каламушлар жалб қилинди. Гистологик таҳлил гепатоцитлар цитоплазмасининг вакуолятсияси, марказий вена тузилишининг бузилиши, жигар синусоидларининг кенгайиши ва Купфер хужайралари фаоллигининг ошишини кўрсатди. Олинган натижалар ўткир буйрак етишмовчилиги жигар паренхимасида сезиларли патологик ўзгаришларни келтириб чиқаришини тасдиқлайди.

Калит сўзлар: ўткир буйрак етишмовчилиги, ҳомиладорлик, жигар морфометрияси, гепатоцит, Купфер хужайралари.

Introduction. Pregnancy is accompanied by profound physiological changes affecting many organ systems, particularly the kidneys and liver. The presence of acute kidney disease (AKD) complicates this physiological adaptation, often leading to severe maternal and fetal complications. Globally, liver pathologies associated with AKD during pregnancy remain among the leading causes of maternal morbidity and mortality. Despite advances in prevention and diagnostics, the mortality associated with liver diseases in pregnancy remains high. Morphometric analysis of the liver offers valuable insights into the structural and functional alterations caused by AKD. In particular, studying experimental models using white rats provides controlled conditions for understanding pathophysiological mechanisms and developing therapeutic interventions. This research addresses the gap in knowledge regarding comparative morphological and morphometric changes of the liver in pregnant rats under conditions of experimentally induced acute renal failure [1,5].

Materials and Methods. A total of 60 white outbred rats (7 months old) were used in this experimental study. Acute renal failure was induced through established experimental protocols one month before pregnancy. The animals were divided into control and experimental groups. Histological examination was performed using liver tissue samples fixed in formalin, embedded in paraffin, and stained with hematoxylin–eosin and Van Gieson methods. Morphometric analysis was carried out using an ocular micrometer (DN-107T, Novel, China). Parameters measured included hepatocyte size, nuclear diameter, sinusoidal spaces, portal triad dimensions, and Kupffer cell counts [4,6]. .

**Micromorphometric parameters of the liver in pregnant white outbred rats
after experimental acute renal failure, μm . ($M \pm m$)**

Histological parameters	Min	Max	Medium
Hepatocyte	1 mm ² -3	1 mm ² -7	1 mm ² -5
Nucleus	1 mm ² -4	1 mm ² --	1 mm ² -5

Width of sinusoids	10MKM	20MKM	15MKM
Cytoplasmic volume	an average of 150 μm per cell ³	an average of 500 μm per cell	an average of 325 μm per cell
Blood vessel diameter			
Hepatic artery	60MKM	160MKM	110MKM
Portal vein diameter	120 μm	320MKM	220MKM
Biliary capillaries	15 MKM	35 MKM	25 MKM

These data characterize the micromorphometric parameters of the liver in pregnant white rats under conditions of experimental acute renal failure. The results show that the values for hepatocytes and their nuclei varied from 1 mm²⁻³ to 1 mm²⁻⁷ and from 1 mm²⁻⁴ to 1 mm²⁻⁵ respectively, with an average value of 1 mm²⁻⁵. However, since these units do not correspond to the standard unit of measurement widely used in morphometric research, their exact content requires additional explanation [2,3].

The width of the liver sinusoids ranged from 10 to 20 μm , averaging 15 μm . These indicators may indicate that certain changes are occurring in the structure of the microcirculatory bed. Analysis of the blood vessel diameter revealed that the diameter of the hepatic artery ranges from 60 to 160 μm , with an average of 110 μm . The diameter of the portal vein is 120–320 μm , with an average value of 220 μm . This confirms that the portal circulatory system is one of the largest vessels in the liver. The diameter of the bile capillaries ranges from 15 to 35 μm , averaging 25 μm .

Overall, the obtained micromorphometric data indicate structural and functional changes in the liver parenchyma and its vascular system under conditions of experimental acute renal failure. However, if the units of measurement for hepatocyte and nuclear parameters are refined into standard morphometric units (μm^2 , μm^2 , or cell density/mm²), the scientific significance and comparability of the results will increase.

Results. Histological evaluation revealed distinct alterations in liver morphology following experimental acute renal failure in pregnant rats: Central vein changes: deformation and narrowing of the central vein walls were frequently observed. Hepatocyte cytoplasm: vacuolization and signs of protein (hydropic and hyaline-droplet) dystrophy were present [9]. Kupfer cells: a significant increase in the number of Kupffer cells indicated ongoing inflammatory and regenerative processes. Binucleated hepatocytes: their number increased, reflecting compensatory and regenerative activity. Sinusoidal spaces: dilation and irregular expansion of Disse's space were documented, suggesting microcirculatory disturbances. Quantitative morphometric analysis demonstrated enlargement of hepatocyte diameters and nuclei, with statistically significant differences compared to controls ($p < 0.01$) [7,8]. Preventive measures, including adequate fluid balance and therapeutic interventions, could mitigate these hepatic alterations. The study also suggests potential value in exploring mineral water therapy (e.g., Juyzar water), rich in trace elements, for supportive management in such conditions.

Conclusion. This experimental study highlights that acute renal failure during pregnancy significantly affects liver morphology and morphometry. Key findings include hepatocyte vacuolization, sinusoidal dilation, Kupffer cell proliferation, and central vein wall deformation. These alterations reflect the complex interplay between renal dysfunction and hepatic adaptation during pregnancy. The results may provide a basis for improved diagnostic criteria, preventive strategies, and therapeutic interventions aimed at reducing complications in pregnant patients with AKD.

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